

ANALYSIS AND CLASSIFICATION OF REMOTELY SENSED SATELLITE DATA USING NEURAL NETWORKS AND FUZZY LOGIC SYSTEMS TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT:

This paper aims at using the various algorithm based neural network techniques and reasoning and logic based fuzzy systems theory to analyze geo spatial remote sensing satellite data for the purposes of data interpretation, pattern recognition, error analysis and classification. A part of the project is thus dedicated to the understanding and implementation of these techniques and analyze their relevance and suitability to the above mentioned exercises. A brief comparative study is then carried out to benchmark the results in comparison with various conventional tools used in this regard. The usefulness of statistical pattern recognition methods including feature selection, feature extraction, decision boundary analysis and data classification are also looked at in both the classical sense as well as from a trainable Neural Network point of view. In conclusion the results obtained from using the commercial MultiSpec[1] software are used to compare the results obtained as outputs from the MATLAB codes written for executing various Neural Network, Fuzzy Logic Theory and Neural Fuzzy Systems algorithms.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Remote Sensing has been conceptualized as the science and art of obtaining information about an object, area or phenomenon through the analysis of data

acquired by a device that is not in contact with the object, area or phenomenon[2]. The data collected may be spatial, spectral or temporal in nature and the features thus established may be represented in the image space, feature space or the signal space. However in this study we concentrate preferably on the feature space representation.

Neural network is defined as a learning process controlled by a learning algorithm, the function of which is to modify the synaptic weights of the network in an orderly fashion to attain a desired design objective. Among the various benefits of neural networks we concentrate on the input-output mapping aspect for the implementation of the project objective.

Other benefits of neural networks that are extensively used implicitly in this study include non-linearity, adaptivity, evidential response, contextual information, mathematical modeling, learning ability, knowledge representation, expert knowledge, optimization, uncertainty tolerance, fault tolerance and real-time operation capabilities[3][4].

Fuzzy logic systems developed from fuzzy sets is defined as mathematical way to represent the vagueness in linguistics and is considered as a generalization of classical set theory. In the course of execution of this project we focus our attention mainly on the use of fuzzy pattern recognition.

Fuzzy systems and neural networks are both considered numerical model-free estimators and dynamical systems and exhibit a property to work in an uncertain, imprecise and noisy environment wherein their capabilities to improve the intelligence of the devices and model complex nonlinear processes to arbitrary degree of accuracy comes to the fore.

The fundamental difference between these two techniques is that while fuzzy systems are *structured numerical estimators*, neural networks on the other hand are *trainable dynamical systems*.

Finally the advantages of neural networks and fuzzy set theory are integrated as part of the neural fuzzy systems that can help develop trainable fuzzy neurons and fuzzy clusters for optimal data clustering and classification.

II. DATA FORMAT AND DESCRIPTION:

The data obtained was a multi-spectral RGB color coded image of an agricultural land mass in north central Indiana. The data was recorded and stored as flight line FIC1.lan.

III. THEORY:

Various functions that have been used in this project include:

Neural networks based –

1. Adaptive linear element learning
2. Back propagation learning
3. Competitive learning
4. Decision tree learning including spilt evaluation function, inaccuracy, entropy and negative gain ratio parameters
5. Error surface analysis
6. Linear vector quantization
7. Perceptron learning
8. Probabilistic neural networks

9. Self-organizing maps

Fuzzy systems based –

1. Fuzzy C-means clustering
2. Sub-clustering

Definitions and Descriptions[3][4]:

1. Adaline learning:

The adaptive linear element learning or the Widrow-Hoff (LMS) learning rule is given by the following set of equations -

$\Delta w_j = \eta (d^{(k)} - w^T x^{(k)}) x_j^{(k)}$ with the minimization of the error function given by

$E(w) = \frac{1}{2} \sum (d^{(k)} - y^{(k)})^2$, $k = 1$ to p where

η = learning rate constant

d = desired output

w = initial weight vector

x = initial input pattern

y = actual output

Thus an array of adalines is a linear network where in each processing element is independent of the other.

2. Back propagation learning:

The back propagation learning is characterized by the following set of equations-

$\Delta w_{iq} = \eta [d_i - y_i][a'(net)][z_q]$

$\Delta v_{pj} = \eta \sum \{ [d_i - y_i][a'(net)] w_{iq} \} [a'(net)] x_j$ with the minimization of the error function given by

$E(w) = \frac{1}{2} \sum (d^{(i)} - y^{(i)})^2$, $i = 1$ to n where

a = specified activation function

The basis for the weight update equations is simply the gradient descent method with the error being propagated backward after each epoch.

3. Competitive learning:

The competitive learning rule is described by

$w_{ij} = s_i (y_i)[s_j (x_j) - w_{ij}]$ where $s_i (y_i) = 1/(1 + \exp(-cy_i))$ and $c = \text{constant}$ with $s = \text{competitive signal}$

This rule is also referred to as the adaptive vector quantization with winner take all nodes.

4. Decision tree:

A decision tree is a series of decisions to determine the class label for a given example. It consists of many nodes and leaves where at each internal node there is a test and a branch corresponding to each of the possible outcomes of the test and at each leaf node there is a class label. Thus a decision tree can be interpreted as a structure in which:

- The root node represents the entire feature space
- Branches emanating from a node represent tests on the value of an attribute
- Each leaf node represents a cell in a partition of the feature space

a. Split evaluation function:

Most decision tree algorithms continue to split until no further splits are possible.

Both the attribute to split and the location of the split along that attribute are chosen to minimize the split evaluation function, SEF, given by

$$SEF = (|t_L| / |t|) * I(t_L) + |t_R| / |t| * I(t_R)$$

Where

t_L and t_R = the left and right splits

t = number of training instances

I = corresponding impurity function given by

$I(t) = I(p_1, \dots, p_c)$ where

p_1, \dots, p_c are the class probability vectors given by

$$p_i = N_i / N$$

$$N = N_1 + N_2 + \dots + N_c.$$

b. Impurity functions:

To produce the smallest tree it is natural to choose the split that brings about the greatest increase in “purity” at each step. Three measures of impurity that have been used in this exercise are –

(i) Inaccuracy:

Inaccuracy is defined by

$$I(p_1, \dots, p_c) = 1 - \max_i p_i$$

5. Error surface analysis:

As a performance measure of a system we may think in terms of the mean square error or the sum of squared error over the training sample defined as a function of the free parameters of the system. This function may be visualized as a multi-dimensional **error performance surface** or simply **error surface** with the free parameters as coordinates. The true error surface is averaged over all possible input-output examples.

(ii) Entropy:

Entropy is defined by

$$E(p_1, \dots, p_c) = -\sum_{i=1}^c p_i \log(p_i), \quad i = 1 \text{ to } c$$

6. Linear vector quantization:

Linear vector quantization is a supervised learning technique that uses class information to improve the quality of the classifier decision regions. The algorithm is given by –

$$w_c(n+1) = w_c(n) \pm \alpha_n [x_i - w_c(n)]$$

for $0 < \alpha_n < 1$.

(iii) Negative gain ratio:

Negative gain ratio is defined by

$$NGR(p_1, \dots, p_c) = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^c p_i^2, \quad i = 1 \text{ to } c$$

where p_i = class probability for the i^{th} class
 c = number of classes

7. Perceptron learning:

The perceptron learning rule is given by $-\Delta w_j = \eta \{d^{(k)} - \text{sgn}(w_j^T x^{(k)})\} x_j^{(k)}$

Hence the training data here are processed one by one with incremental weight adjustment to find the optimum decision plane where

sgm = either a unipolar or bipolar sigmoid function given by

$$\text{sgm}(-\lambda f) = 1 / \{1 + \exp(-\lambda f)\} \text{ or}$$

$$\text{sgm}(-\lambda f) = [2 / \{1 + \exp(-\lambda f)\}] - 1$$

8. Probabilistic neural networks:

The probabilistic neural networks essentially deals with the estimation of the probability density measure and is well suited for data which have normal gaussian distribution given by -

$$f_A(X) = \{1 / (2\pi)^{n/2} \sigma^n\} * (1/m_A) * \sum \exp \{ - (X - X_{Ai})^T (X - X_{Ai}) / \{2\sigma^2\} \}$$

where

X_{Ai} = i^{th} training pattern from class A

X = input vector

m_A = mean vector of class A

Note: the presence of non-linearity in the data and hence the absence of a regular hyper plane in both the figures above

9. Self-organizing maps:

Self-organizing maps are essentially feature maps that convert patterns of arbitrary dimensionality into the responses of one or two-dimensional arrays of neurons. In addition to dimensionality reduction they preserve neighborhood

relations of the input pattern. One approach to design a SOM is to use the Kohonen's winner take all learning rule given by –

Similarity matching: $\|x - w_i^{(k)}\| = \min \{\|x - w_j^{(k)}\|\}$ for $1 \leq j \leq n$

Updating: $w_i^{(k+1)} = w_i^{(k)} + \alpha^{(k)} \{x - w_i^{(k)}\}$

$$w_j^{(k+1)} = w_j^{(k)}$$

where $w_i^{(k)}$ is the normalized weight vector given by

$$w_i^{(k)} = w_i / \|w_i\|$$

10. Fuzzy C-means clustering:

The fuzzy criterion in clustering is to optimize an objective function that acts as a performance index, the end result being expressed by a partition matrix. The fuzzy conditions are given by –

$$v_i = [1/\{\sum_j (u_{ij})^m\}] \sum_j (u_{ij})^m x_j \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, c \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

$$u_{ij} = \{(1/\|x_j - v_i\|^2)^{1/(m-1)}\} / \sum_k \{(1/\|x_j - v_k\|^2)^{1/(m-1)}\} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, c \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ and } k = 1, 2, \dots, c$$

Note: the presence of non-linearity in the data and hence the absence of a regular hyper plane

10. Sub-clustering:

Sub-clustering is a technique where the cluster centers are estimated from subtractive clustering.

IV. PROCEDURE AND METHODOLOGY:

1. Digitization of the satellite image to get the required training vectors for each of the classes. The classes that were decided include -

- (i) corn
- (ii) roadways
- (iii) railways
- (iv) soybean
- (v) waterbody
- (vi) wasteland
- (vii) red clover
- (viii) wheat

2. Feeding the data as a set of (x,y) coordinates to various MATLAB codes to generate the required output.

3. Carrying out feature extraction, clustering and classification exercises.

4. Comparing the test and training data accuracy with that obtained from MULTISPEC software.

5. Presenting the final results and drawing conclusions from the results.

- Classes**
- background
 - corn
 - red clover
 - wheat
 - waste land
 - soybean
 - roadways
 - railway
 - water body

fig3: classified map of the study area

- Groups**
- background
 - 0-1
 - 1-2
 - 2-3
 - 3-4
 - 4-5
 - 5-10
 - 10-20
 - 20-30
 - 30-40
 - 40-50
 - 50-60
 - 60-70
 - 70-80
 - 80-90
 - 90-100

fig4: probability distribution map

- Groups**
- background
 - Cluster 1
 - Cluster 2
 - Cluster 3
 - Cluster 4
 - Cluster 5
 - Cluster 6

fig5: cluster mask map

TABLE: 1 FEATURE EXTRACTION RESULTS FROM MULTISPEC

Feature Extraction 03-21-2002 17:31:45
 (MultiSpec6.30.99)
 Project = 'FLC.PRJ'
 Base image file = 'FLC1.LAN'

Classes used:	Weight
1: corn	10.000
2: red clover	10.000
3: wheat	10.000
4: waste land	10.000
5: soybean	10.000
6: roadways	10.000
7: railway	10.000
8: water body	10.000

All class pairs will be used.

Channels used:

- 1: 0.40- 0.44 μm
- 2: 0.44- 0.46 μm
- 3: 0.46- 0.48 μm
- 4: 0.48- 0.50 μm
- 5: 0.50- 0.52 μm
- 6: 0.52- 0.55 μm
- 7: 0.55- 0.58 μm
- 8: 0.58- 0.62 μm
- 9: 0.62- 0.66 μm
- 10: 0.66- 0.72 μm
- 11: 0.72- 0.80 μm
- 12: 0.80- 1.00 μm

No Feature Extraction Preprocessing will be done.

Feature Extraction will be done with:

Decision Boundary Technique

Minimum threshold number = 5.

Within class threshold = 0.95.

Between class threshold = 0.95.

Class optimization threshold = 95 percent.

Approximate maximum number of pixels per class = 1000.

Number of data values in each class pair, number of values meeting class thresholds and number of features required for each class pair to meet optimization percent.

Final Feature Extraction Transformation Matrix

Component	Eigenvalue	Percent	Cum.	'Cum.'	Cum.	Feature
	Percent	'Determinant'				
	'Log Det.'	'Mean'				
1	7.4565	30.1990				
30.1990		7.4565e+000				
	2.0091e+000	-23.21				
2	4.0638	16.4584				
46.6574		3.0301e+001				
	3.4112e+000	-42.49				
3	3.4923	14.1438				
60.8012		1.0582e+002				
	4.6617e+000	6.42				
4	2.5550	71.1489				
2.7037e+002		5.5998e+000				
5	2.2669	19.64				
80.3301		9.1812				
	6.4182e+000	6.1291e+002				
6	1.7939	18.78				
87.5953		7.2652				
	7.0026e+000	1.0995e+003				
7	1.1432	-2.78				
92.2252		4.6299				
	7.1364e+000	1.2569e+003				
8	0.7431	44.07				
95.2348		3.0096				
	6.8395e+000	9.3399e+002				
9	0.5699	-24.91				
97.5430		2.3082				
	6.2772e+000	5.3231e+002				
10	0.3625	-10.89				
99.0113		1.4683				
	5.2626e+000	1.9298e+002				
11	0.1516	132.58				
99.6253		0.6140				
	3.3761e+000	2.9256e+001				
		233.00				

12 0.0925 0.3747
 100.0000 2.7068e+000
 9.9576e-001 -23.26

End one pass cluster

**89 CPU seconds for feature extraction.
 03-21-2002 17:33:14**

**36 CPU seconds for clustering. 03-28-
 2002 15:02:53**

**TABLE: 2 CLUSTER STATISTICS
 FROM MULTISPEC**

Cluster 03-28-2002 15:02:17
 (MultiSpec6.30.99)
 Project = 'FLC1.PRJ'
 Base image file = 'flc1.lan'
 Image start line and column = 1, 1
 Clusters from selected area.
 Lines: 1 to 949 by 1
 Columns: 1 to 220 by 5

The cluster statistics will be saved to the
 project file.

Cluster classify training area(s).

Channels used:
 1: 0.40- 0.44 μm
 2: 0.44- 0.46 μm
 3: 0.46- 0.48 μm
 4: 0.48- 0.50 μm
 5: 0.50- 0.52 μm
 6: 0.52- 0.55 μm
 7: 0.55- 0.58 μm
 8: 0.58- 0.62 μm
 9: 0.62- 0.66 μm
 10: 0.66- 0.72 μm
 11: 0.72- 0.80 μm
 12: 0.80- 1.00 μm

Start one pass cluster
 Critical distance 1: 17
 Critical distance 2: 34
 Minimum cluster size: 13

Number of total clusters = 63
 Number of final clusters = 33

Number of pixels not classified = 0

**TABLE: 3 CLASSIFICATION
 RESULTS FROM MULTISPEC**

Classify 03-21-2002 17:34:39
 (MultiSpec6.30.99)
 Project = 'FLC.PRJ'
 Base image file = 'FLC1.LAN'
 Image start line and column = 1, 1
 Target image file = 'FLC1.LAN'
 Number classes = 9
 Number classes used = 8
 Start maximum likelihood classification

Classes used:	Weight	Symbol
0: Threshold (background)		''
1: corn	10.000	1
2: red clover	10.000	2
3: wheat	10.000	3
4: waste land	10.000	4
5: soybean	10.000	5
6: roadways	10.000	6
7: railway	10.000	7
8: water body	10.000	8

Training Fields Used: (line interval = 1;
 column interval = 1)

Field name	First Last		Class	Line
	Line	Col. Col.		
1: Field 1	186	210	107	205
2: Field 2	221	260	5	35

51: Field 51				7
882	884	186	202	
52: Field 52				7
892	894	130	146	
53: Field 53				7
911	915	82	86	
54: Field 54				8
906	912	42	91	
55: Field 55				8
687	696	100	108	
56: Field 56				8
195	204	88	96	
57: Field 57				8
236	261	86	102	

Channels used:

- 1: 0.40- 0.44 μm
- 2: 0.44- 0.46 μm
- 3: 0.46- 0.48 μm
- 4: 0.48- 0.50 μm
- 5: 0.50- 0.52 μm
- 6: 0.52- 0.55 μm
- 7: 0.55- 0.58 μm
- 8: 0.58- 0.62 μm
- 9: 0.62- 0.66 μm
- 10: 0.66- 0.72 μm
- 11: 0.72- 0.80 μm
- 12: 0.80- 1.00 μm

Threshold percent: 0.0

corn	1	70.0	25814	
	18058	4507	1319	
5	1026	439	321	105
			34	
red clover	2	84.1	1701	
211	1431	2	0	
15	24	13	5	0
wheat	3	89.8	30064	
	597	59	26996	65
1071	414	602	215	
		45		
waste land	4	98.4	3477	
4	2	1	3421	
1	6	20	7	15
soybean	5	52.3	72484	
	15113	1082	15789	
44	37895	845	1021	561
			134	
roadways	6	50.3	1141	
136	27	53	11	48
	574	211	74	7
railway	7	80.1	136	
3	0	8	1	4
	7	109	4	0
water body	8	32.7	972	
115	7	84	4	44
130	234	318		36
TOTAL				
135789		34237	7115	
44252	3551		40104	2439
	2531	1289		271

Reliability Accuracy (%)*

	52.7	20.1
61.0	96.3	94.5
23.5	4.3	24.7

TRAINING CLASS PERFORMANCE
(Resubstitution Method)

Project	Reference			
	Number of Samples in Class			
Class	Class		Accuracy+	
	Number	1	2	
3	4	5	6	7
	8	Threshold		
Name	Number	(%)		
	Samples	corn	red clover	
	wheat	waste land	soybean	
	roadways	railway	water body	

OVERALL CLASS PERFORMANCE

$(88802 / 135789) = 65.4\%$

Kappa Statistic (X100) = 52.0%. Kappa

Variance = 0.000003.

+ (100 - percent omission error); also called producer's accuracy.

* (100 - percent commission error); also called user's accuracy.

End maximum likelihood classification

9 CPU seconds for classification. 03-21-

2002 17:34:48

VI. OBSERVATIONS:

1. The competitive learning algorithm indicated a very marginal error after 1800 epochs, however the data points showed non-linear behavior.
2. A similar result was depicted from the probabilistic neural network-learning algorithm.
3. The perceptron-learning rule indicated a wrongly plotted decision boundary hyper plane indicating non-linearity in the data.
4. The subclust program produced cluster centers using the subtractive clustering technique, these points on joining showed a linear behavior.

Cluster centers are given by --

C =

110 0 0 0 99 0 0 0

The range of influence of a cluster center in each of the data dimensions is given by

--

S = 167.0540 163.6952 144.2498
128.6934 166.1701 165.4630 161.2203
143.1891

A range of influence of 0.5 has been specified for all data dimensions.

VII. COMPARATIVE STUDY:

- On using the **MultiSpec** software a training accuracy of **65.4%** was

obtained while the predetermined test accuracy was in the range of **75-85%** for the end classification statistic. In this procedure the conventional pattern recognition methods including decision boundary feature extraction, statistical clustering and maximum likelihood classification were used.

- With the error surface command an error matrix that was in the range of 10^{-15} was observed while the sum of squared error, **SSE**, turned out to be **2.7980 * 10⁻³⁰**.
- With the fuzzy C-means clustering the net error, **FCN**, was found to be **0** after about 12 iterations.
- The distribution of weights after training for 50 epochs was found to be more uniform during the execution of the self-organizing map, **SOM**. The net change in weight tends to **zero**.
- From the **decision tree** program the value of the **negative gain ratio** obtained was **0.054054**, that of **entropy** was **0.054054** and finally the **inaccuracy** was found to be **0.094595**. These results were found for 6, 4 & 11 nodes respectively and 74 leaves each. These values were small indicating optimal performance with acceptable results.
- The adaptive linear element, **ADALINE**, program yielded a performance of 0.168776 with a goal of 0.10 indicating an error of **31.224%** or an accuracy of **68.776%**, while the end data points after simulation were found to be linearly distributed. This

accuracy was higher than the one obtained from MultiSpec.

- The linear vector quantization, **LVQ**, algorithm produced a **50%** accuracy and hence an error of **50%**. However it accounted for the non-linearity in the data with the final data points and simulated weight vectors indicating linear behavior.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS AND INFERENCES:

The conclusions and inferences that were drawn from the observations and comparative study include –

- Learning algorithm based neural network techniques and set theory based fuzzy systems showed on average better results in terms of accuracy as these procedures work on the principle of error minimization. Excepting for the LVQ algorithm all other procedures gave better results than those obtained from MultiSpec software.
- The second advantage with these procedures was the minimization of biases by randomizing the data.
- Finally these algorithms helped capture non-linearity to a greater extent and most end results after simulation plotted linear classified data points.
- MultiSpec software with classical pattern recognition tools performed well with linear data that was not correlated and was normally distributed. This may well be stated as a limitation of the software. Also randomizing the data was not possible. However

the program would be ideal when performing dimensionality reduction and other such exercises. Also it provides user-friendly techniques to perform feature extraction, clustering, principle component analysis, feature selection apart from having a great advantage of being able to produce quality end classification maps that are helpful for the purposes of presentation and facilitate easy understanding and interpretation.

- This exercise has helped me understand the relevance and usefulness in the techniques of neural networks and fuzzy systems in the study of geo-spatial data for the purposes of analysis, classification and prediction. It has been noted that these techniques were superior to the conventional existing techniques in some areas like in capturing the non – linearity in the data and error minimization while the conventional techniques like the maximum likelihood classification in combination with the decision boundary feature extraction technique performed with superior accuracy when the data was linear and well distributed.

IX. FUTURE WORK:

It is proposed to use, in the future techniques from machine learning, data mining and genetic algorithms to classify the same data set and evaluate their performance with respect to the performance of neural networks, fuzzy logic theory and neural fuzzy systems apart from statistical pattern recognition methods to establish which technique works better for a given

data set and a given set of constraints.

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